

THE IMPORTANCE OF FORMING LOGICAL THINKING IN YOUNG PEOPLE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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Annotation: Every day, we are faced with numerous jobs that demand us to think logically in order to solve. In fact, according to "official logic," the appropriate mindset among many people can be founded on experience and so-called common sense, rather than on the idea of applying laws and particular procedures. To conduct simple logic operations, the initial suggestion and statements of simple conclusions can frequently lead to errors in general sense and common sense, and if you know or grasp anything more sophisticated. In this post, we will address the significance of developing logical thinking in young people for the advancement of civilization.

Keywords: young people, spatial imagination, logical thinking, ability, Development, importance of Education, society.

In our perspective, a person's logical thinking and emotional ability should be cultivated on a regular basis, using specialized terminology and logical ways. In the online training class, you will learn self-education techniques for the development of logical thinking, as well as the main categories, characteristics of principles, and laws of logic, as well as examples and exercises for applying acquired knowledge and skills, such as what is logical thinking and spatial imagination, and how to develop them.

It is well established that modeling is one of the most effective forms of classroom activity for developing kids' spatial imagination. The didactic benefit of such activities is that they not only make it easier to envision the spatial qualities and relationships of the described object, but they also help to better understand all of the remaining information based on the drawing. The essence of this strategy is the formation of mental activity inherent in the imaginative process. Practical alterations in appearance during the modeling process will serve as the foundation for the development of the essential mental activity. During the modeling process, the student not only senses the appearance of the body, but also engages in activities such as organism construction, logical analysis, and distribution through skin sensation.

So, logical reasoning? To define "logical thinking," we divide it into two parts: thinking and logic. Logical thinking-a mental process in which a person's goal is to judge, and which is characterized by the application of logical concepts and

the design of evidence, with the goal of getting the sound coming out of the existing premises. Let us define each of these elements. Thinking about a person is a mental activity that involves processing information and developing associations between items, their attributes, or occurrences in the surrounding environment. Thinking enables a person to discover the link between reality's occurrences, but communication, of course, thought, in other words, discovered that the object properly reflect the actual state of affairs or should be, it is logical that logic is subject.

There are numerous translations from the Greek language of logic: "right thinking," "the art of thinking," "speaking," and even "thinking ". In our situation, one of the most reasonable definitions is that we act as a normative science of the forms, techniques, and laws of human intellectual activity. The logic is not an emotional experiment, but rather a study of methods of reaching truth in the educational process through mediation, but it is also pushed forward, to take on information, and therefore it may be regarded as the science of how to get out of knowledge.

Use logical means in practically all areas of human activity, including concrete and humanitarian, economics and business, rhetoric and lectures, creative processes and creations. In some fields, such as mathematics, philosophy, and technology, precise and codified logic is applied. In other circumstances, logic is only effective for drawing conclusions in economic, historical, or basic "living" conditions.

Of course, everyone uses logic as a description, categorization and classification, confirmation, rejection, denial, imagination, and so on in his or her mental activity. However, we utilize them instinctively and frequently improperly, so you are unaware of the depth and complexity of their mental processes. The most crucial part of visualizing is visual-spatial imagination. The act of visualizing allows you to use your imagination to create whatever you want. In our scenario, a consistent image of power and open channels is required. Otherwise, how can we control the electricity if we don't see it? Visualization occurs first, followed by true perception.

The conclusion is the third mode of thought, in which one, two, or more debts are referred to as packages, and a new proposal is made, referred to as conclusions or conclusions. The same compositional style is used to transmit this enigmatic Infinity to readers and to make them feel this dynamic atmosphere. Furthermore, the use of information technology and media sources such as video, photographs, and audio will help students build spatial

imagination. Students should be taught complex methods and be able to describe and apply them in simple words. This needs the use of a highly qualified educator. It is also critical to analyze how students differ in terms of knowledge and thinking. Several writing strategies are commonly used in this process. The most crucial aspect is that spatial thinking growth is founded on knowledge, vision, hearing, and perception.

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